

Recharge

PLAYBOOK

on Participatory Cultural Business Models

RECHARGE
Resilient European Cultural Heritage
As Resource for Growth & Engagement

Funded by
the European Union

Version 1.0 January 2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Cultural Participatory Business Models for Financial Sustainability & Social Responsibility	03
All you need to know before you get started	04
Co-designing the Living Lab	12
Identify Key Stakeholders	14
Set up and Run Co-creation Workshops	17
Set up your Living Lab	28
Running a Living Lab Project	33
Evaluation of LL Results Against KPIs	36
Living Lab Sample Toolbox	38
What is the Recharge Platform?	48
Annex: Recharge Glossary	52

CULTURAL PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELS FOR FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY & SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

The viability of a cultural organisation is linked to the value it delivers to its target communities, however, this does not guarantee financial stability. So how do we create societal impact under sustainable business models?

The RECHARGE Playbook proposes that community participation can reinvigorate the cultural sector by offering paths for more sustainable business models. By tapping into the needs and resources available in existing communities - whether that's volunteer groups or corporate partners - cultural organisations can increase their relevance and support their operations with diversified financing routes.

What is the RECHARGE Playbook?

The RECHARGE playbook is a practical guide to ensure that participation in culture is integral to the financial sustainability of your organisation. It presents 9 Cultural Participatory Business Models that can extend your already existing operations or help you introduce new services / products. In the playbook you will find ready-to-use processes and examples on how to implement these business models using a Living Labs methodology.

This playbook is for anyone working with cultural heritage who wishes to explore how to better financially support long-term participation. No previous experience working with business models is needed!

To make the most out of this playbook:

This playbook explains what Cultural Participatory Business Models are and why they can help with supporting participation, how you can use the Living Lab methodology to experiment with and test participatory business models, and why it's helpful to have a shared language when working with others.

To make the most out of this playbook:

- To make the most out of this playbook and fully understand the canvases and exercises, we recommend to follow the playbook from start to finish

ALL YOU NEED TO KNOW BEFORE YOU GET STARTED

THE FOLLOWING PAGES OF THE
PLAYBOOK WILL EXPLAIN:

05

What Cultural Participatory
Business Models are and why
they can help with supporting
participation

10

How you can use the Living
Lab methodology to
experiment with and test
participatory business models

11

Why it's helpful to have a
shared language when working
with others

WHAT ARE CULTURAL PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELS?

Integrating a Business Model

Why think about a business model? It can help to develop sustainable financing. A business model can support you and your organisation in identifying how to monetise or fund what your audience finds valuable and how to develop relationships, services, or even products that deliver that value.

In simple terms, a business model is all about the "why" and "how" of an organisation's success – how it creates, delivers, and grabs hold of the value it offers to the world.

Imagine a business model as the "big picture" plan. It is the backbone defining who the organisation serves, what its customers, users, visitors, or participants find valuable, and how the organisation and beneficiary community or communities make money by providing that value.

When thinking about a business model, consider three aspects:

- **Value creation** refers to the development of products or services that an organisation offers on the basis of its participants or stakeholder needs. Do they want what is offered?
- **Value delivery refers** to the necessary processes that are set in place to bring products or services to customers. Can the offer be delivered?
- **Value capturing** refers to the results of the value delivery process. These can be understood in the form of revenues (monetary), reach (the amount of people who benefit from the offered products and services), and reputation (the improvement of the organisation's image). Is the offer worthy?

Recharge Approach to Cultural Participatory Business Models

Perhaps you have worked with business models before and even used a business model canvas. What makes a Cultural Participatory Business Model different is the **added layers of a participatory approach, a focus on social value, and the perspective of cultural heritage institutions**. This includes a focus on social value proposition, and accounting for both social and environmental costs and benefits. By incorporating the perspectives of multiple actors throughout the collaboration process, stakeholders can present their needs and advocate for their shares of the benefits. Working in this way can contribute to the long-term sustainability of your initiative by strengthening inclusion and supporting democratic processes.

PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE INSTITUTIONS

RECHARGE (RESILIENT EUROPEAN CULTURAL HERITAGE AS RESOURCE FOR GROWTH AND ENGAGEMENT) RECHARGE-CULTURE.EU

The Participatory Business Model Canvas (CPBM) can be useful in different ways, including:

1. Highlighting the role of participation and engagement of different stakeholders throughout the entire business modelling;
2. Linking different aspects of a business model into one coherent approach for cultural heritage institutions;
3. Guiding the participatory innovation process in cultural institutions;
4. Helping to communicate the participatory elements of the institution's business plan.

This playbook proposes eight distinct participatory business models plus one hybrid model combining elements across different models. Each model represents different focus areas for business model innovation.

CULTURAL PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELS

CPBM	Social Value Proposition
COLLABORATIVE E-COMMERCE MODEL	An online shop is shared by several CHIs, products and services are developed in collaboration with the local creative community.
REVENUE SHARING INNOVATION MODEL	The CHIs are co-creators and co-owners of innovative products or services and adopt appropriate revenue-sharing mechanisms to create long-term financial benefits.
CSR CULTURAL HERITAGE COMMUNITY MODEL	Companies use their corporate social responsibility (CSR) or environmental, social, and governance (ESG) programmes to benefit both CHIs and communities.
COMMUNITY CROWDSOURCING MODEL	Communities are involved in content creation, ideation, implementation, and financing of CHI products and initiatives.
PARTICIPATORY DISTRIBUTION MODEL	The CHIs products and services are disseminated and distributed by an open community network.

CULTURAL PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELS

CPBM	Social Value Proposition
ASSET AND RESOURCE SHARING MODEL	The CHIs are using external shared assets for their core activities and provide their own assets for community use.
OPEN-SOURCE SERVICE MODEL	The CHIs provide licence-free open access to their services and content for community use.
ON-DEMAND SERVICE MODEL	The CHIs offer tailor-made content and service solutions addressing specific needs of users, including communities, organisations, and other stakeholders.
EXTRA: HYBRID MODEL	A hybrid model in which the CHIs mix different elements of some or all previously mentioned participatory business models.

IMPLEMENTING CULTURAL PARTICIPATORY BUSINESS MODELS THE LIVING LABS APPROACH

What is a Living Lab?

Living Labs is a methodology commonly used in many sectors as well as the cultural sector to support working with various stakeholders and communities towards solutions that add or cultivate financial, social, and cultural value.

Why use Living Labs? By design, participatory business models aim to tackle challenges that affect various stakeholders and they require all of those stakeholders to be engaged in the process of finding sustainable solutions as well as contributing resources (time, knowledge, money) towards it. Living Labs match this need by operating as open innovation ecosystems where diverse groups collaborate to drive positive change through practical projects in real-world settings. For example, the Hunt Museum in Ireland wanted to address anti-social behaviour in the museum garden. Using the Living Labs methodology, they were able to involve other museums, local citizens and corporate organisations in co-creating and implementing a solution - a willow weaving programme in the museum's garden.

FACILITATING PARTICIPATION THROUGH SHARED LANGUAGE

The Recharge Glossary

Working in a Living Lab means co-creation with people who come from different sectors, hold different values and come with different ideas about issues at hand. A shared vocabulary can ease communication and collaboration. The RECHARGE Glossary will help you develop shared understanding about the main elements of the cultural participatory business models and the process of implementing them.

Checkout the Recharge Glossary in the Annex!

01. CO-DESIGNING THE LIVING LAB

Recognising Opportunity

Where should the impulse for exploring Cultural Participatory Business Models come from?

- Your organisation might already have an activity that relies on a business model that needs revision, or you are looking for ways how to strengthen it by involving other stakeholders;
- You might have an idea for a new service - for instance, an online gift shop or an educational service - that needs a sustainable business model;
- Your organisation's strategy has identified a specific impact area - for instance, find ways to support local artists better - and you are in the process on brainstorming ideas how to realise it;
- You identified a specific challenge - like anti-social behaviour in a museum garden - that requiring novel approaches and access to resources you currently do not have.

This starting point defines the scope of the challenge you will focus on in your Living Lab.

From here you can start brainstorming - you can create a mind map with potential ideas. The point of this exercise is not to find the exact solution but to identify potential areas of investigation and stakeholders who could help you turn these ideas into an actionable plan.

Based on this mind map, you can start filling out the CPBM Canvas with your initial ideas. Some sections might remain empty or you might fill them with questions that need to be answered as you conduct your Living Lab.

Looking at your initial CPBM Canvas, think about which of the 9 Cultural Participatory Business Models could provide suitable solutions for your problem. You don't need to commit to a particular model just yet - but this will be a helpful starting point for your conversations with stakeholders.

Before you move to the next step, check if you have done the following:

- Identify one concrete challenge or problem that you would like to like to tackle
- Fill out the CPBM Canvas with your initial ideas
- Ideate which Cultural Participatory Business Models could help you to address the selected challenge

02. IDENTIFY KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholder Mapping

After filling out your initial CPBM Canvas, you can get started with stakeholder mapping - an exercise to identify all actors who have a stake in the questions raised by your Living Lab. This will help to ensure that the process is truly participatory and that the right stakeholders are involved at the proper stages to design and execute a successful participatory business model.

Use one of the already existing stakeholder mapping tools to visualise your stakeholders and their needs (check out the [Living Labs Sample Toolbox chapter](#) for examples). Do not be afraid to adjust or combine the tools to suit your needs. Start by identifying stakeholder group types (for instance, corporate organisations, local communities or creatives) and then match them with specific names of organisations or persons you would like to engage.

Stakeholder mapping is an iterative exercise - you will have to come back to it and update it as your Living Lab process takes shape. For instance, during initial engagement with the Living Lab participants, you might identify a new stakeholder group that needs to be involved. Come back to your stakeholder mapping visualisation at regular intervals to check that all relevant stakeholders are engaged. "An important note is to be conscientious and considerate of developing stakeholder engagement practices that support more diverse participants with equitable and inclusive spaces and conditions for work and collaboration. Supporting more diverse stakeholder engagement might mean creating space for participation for historically underrepresented groups, which in mapping could translate to identifying issues and interests of different communities, finding common ground, and tailoring an engagement and communication strategy in your outreach.

In the mapping of external stakeholders, consider actors who are integral to the execution of the Living Lab and need to take part in the participatory decision-making process. Your selected CPBM and the specific project idea determine who belongs to this group. This might range from other heritage organisations and commercial entities to local community organisations and individual citizens. Depending on the motivations and expertise each stakeholder brings, the Living Lab can determine the specific decisions and stages of the process that they should be involved in.

Stakeholder management

Once you have an initial version of your stakeholder mapping done, translate it into a stakeholder management document. Here, you can define more specific approaches for the engagement of each individual stakeholder. We suggest including the following:

- Stakeholder contact person - make sure to identify a specific person within the stakeholder organisation who will be your contact;
- Motivation - what drives their engagement in the Living Lab;
- Roles - what they contribute and what roles they can take on in the Living Lab;
- Who is responsible for communicating with them - in most cases, this will be the Community Manager;
- Participatory approaches - activities that they will be part of in the Living Lab process;
- Communication tracker - keeping a track record of communication with this stakeholder and activities they took part in.

Stakeholders in Your Organisations

Who within your organisation should be part of the Living Lab? Next to stakeholders that your organisation will collaborate with, each Living Lab needs a motivated team of colleagues to run the participatory process. We propose the following roles (you might find that one person takes on multiple roles or that a role is shared between multiple people):

- **Living Lab lead** - a person who carries the vision of the Living Lab and oversees its design, execution and evaluation following the process described in this Playbook. They also advocate for the uptake of the CPMB in the organisation's long-term strategy.
- **Community manager** - a contact person for all external stakeholders engaged in the Living Lab process. They are responsible for managing relationships and ensuring all stakeholders are informed about the Living Lab activities and feel comfortable engaging in the process.
- **Financial manager** - a person who identifies resources needed to execute the Living Lab and manages their use. They also help define how resources generated through the CPBM can support the organisation's long-term financial sustainability.

- **Marketing & communication** - a person who oversees the marketing and communication strategy, including producing communication materials tailored for different stakeholder groups.

You will also need to add roles are specific to your Living Lab activities - this will depend on your Living Lab project and the chosen CPMB.

Consider also how you will engage your organisation's management team - you might need to consult and get their approval at different stages of implementing the Living Lab. While they might not be actively engaged in the Living Lab process, you will need to communicate with them proactively to ensure that the CPMB is positioned within the organisation's strategy.

If you find that your organisation lacks the right expertise and skills to lead the living labs process, consider working with an outside expert - for instance, you might want to hire an external consultant or facilitator. Use this playbook to scope their assignment.

Before you move to the next step, check if you have done the following:

- Initial mapping of stakeholders
- Onboarding of internal team members and division of roles
- Set up a stakeholder management document

03. SET UP AND RUN CO-IDEATION WORKSHOPS

Now that you know who your key stakeholders are, it is time to start organising co-ideation workshops to turn ideas into a concrete project plan for the selected CPBM. This is a funnelling process - start with many ideas coming from different perspectives and narrow it down to a more specific focus that addresses specific societal needs and matches resources available between the participating stakeholders.

- Start by identifying questions that your Living Lab would like to address. Try to group and prioritise them and identify which stakeholders you need to engage to generate ideas around them.
- Once you have the overview of questions, consider how many co-ideation workshops you would need. Take into account the number of people you would like to engage as well as time/resource constraints.

The three first generation RECHARGE Living Labs opted for in-person co-ideation workshops over virtual ones, recognising the value of face-to-face interaction. While virtual setups are feasible, nothing beats the genuine connections and comfortable atmosphere that in-person meetings offer. Think comfortable spaces, friendly conversations, and the added bonus of sharing teas, coffees, snacks, and, in some instances, even a delightful museum tour!

These workshops, held over a single day, welcomed no more than 30 participants each, ensuring a conducive environment for open discussions. The actual attendance depended on available space and the facilitators' ability to split larger groups into more intimate settings for fruitful exchanges.

The primary goal was to create an inviting space where ideas flowed naturally and participants felt empowered to share their thoughts. The mix of a relaxed setting, great company, and a stimulating environment truly sparked innovative thinking!

Agenda for the Co-Ideation Workshop

When setting the workshop agenda, include plenary sessions to introduce the goals and context as well as some inspirational sessions (for instance, sharing examples from similar collaborations). But the majority of time should be reserved for discussion and collaborative co-ideation activities in small groups.

Example: Agenda for the Hunt Museum Living Lab co-ideation workshop with corporates and museums

Time	Activity
10.00	Arrival- tea, coffee, scones
10.15	Opening of the workshop - Aim of the day & round of introductions
10.30	Introduction to RECHARGE Project and role of the Hunt Museum and Humanli
10.45	Plenary Session
12.45	Lunch
13.15	Case-studies: Previous examples where and how the Hunt Museum has co-created with companies (Takumi, Arup/ESB)
13.30	Ideating Living Lab Projects in break-out groups
14.30	Presentation of project ideas and discussion on possible implementation of selected pilot initiatives.
15.00	Next steps for the RECHARGE Living Labs - application of participatory business modelling, involving relevant communities.
15.30	End of the workshop and a tour of the Hunt Museum Collection

Value Proposition

Invitation to the co-ideation workshop might be one of your first interactions with the future participants of your Living Labs. Make sure to clearly and effectively communicate the value proposition of your Living Lab. Why is it worth it for them to be engaged in the process? Why should they dedicate their time and resources to co-creating with you? What will they gain in return for their participation? And what impact will they create for your organisations and the target communities?

Your value proposition should be a short pitch answering these questions. Keep different stakeholder groups and their needs in mind as you formulate your value proposition - you might need to adjust it based on who you are communicating it to.

Example: Value proposition communicated by the Prato Museum Living Lab

Validating the value proposition of the future PratoTextile Museum business model was the main goal of our co-ideation workshop. We knew we wanted to go in the direction of developing an e-shop to serve local professional communities - such as other small museums, designers and artisans, small manufacturing companies and fine arts and design academies - but we were not sure which should be the exact value proposition of e-commerce.

Therefore, we have invited several representatives of the above mentioned professional categories and designed the workshop proposing three different value propositions:

1. Museum e-shops as platforms to support and endorse emergent, environmentally-aware art, design and crafts projects.
2. Museum e-shops as tools for local-regional heritage and culture promotion.
3. Museum e-shops as a knowledge, learning and research hub.

Divided in three groups, one per each value proposition, the participants have designed a proof of e-shop concept per each value proposition, highlighting the key elements of each of them.

Thanks to the insights emerged by the workshop, we were able to identify a single and unique value proposition, aimed at making museum e-shops cool, edutaining, go-to places for locally and ethically sourced, sustainability-oriented quality products. Consequently, we were able to develop a detailed participatory business model canvas.

Example: Value proposition communicated by the Estonian Maritime Museum Living Lab

What we offered - a hub where cultural heritage organisations, tech visionaries, researchers, and community advocates converge with a shared goal: to propel cultural heritage into a new era. The Living Lab co-ideation workshop is our brainchild, crafted to foster innovation by harnessing the unique strengths of diverse stakeholders.

For CHIs, this isn't just another workshop – it's a chance to shape the very future they preserve. By teaming up with peer institutions, participants actively contribute to evolving cultural heritage practices. It's a dual win – not only are they part of groundbreaking solutions, but they also position themselves at the forefront of progressive cultural practices, attracting new audiences along the way.

(Ed)Tech innovators find a goldmine in our Living Lab. It's more than a testing ground; it's a real-world arena where innovation meets validation. By participating, tech pioneers receive crucial feedback from cultural heritage experts, fine-tuning their products to meet sector-specific needs. The Living Lab isn't just about solutions; it's a gateway to forging meaningful partnerships with cultural institutions, creating projects that seamlessly blend technology and cultural heritage.

Co-creation Activities

Deciding how to structure your co-ideation workshops and what co-creation techniques to use will highly depend on the questions you want to answer. You can find a selection of possible approaches in the [Living Lab sample box section](#) but feel free to use any co-creation methods that you feel comfortable with.

Whatever activities you choose for your co-ideation workshop, make sure you create an open and inclusive space:

- Minimise jargon and explain terms - remember that terminology that is obvious to you might not be familiar to people from other domains;
- Encourage everyone to participate - consider different ways for participants to provide input (verbal and written);
- Foster constructive dialogue and criticism in between participants, this will help leveraging on collective intelligence.

Example: Here is how Estonian Maritime Museum selected workshop techniques and tools based on their specific stakeholder groups

Sometimes, to move forward, it's essential to discover where the "pain" is most intense. This knowledge guides us to understand which kind of "band-aid" is needed. In our third co-ideation workshop, our primary participants were teachers, whose invaluable work we aimed to support. To address the challenges they face, we sifted through the ideas gathered in previous workshops and identified a concept: using augmented reality to add a virtual layer of visual information to the physical environment, namely the classroom.

Before presenting our thoughts, we listened to the teachers express their "pain." In fact, we didn't even finish the introductions before the passion of the teachers for their work vividly illustrated the locked gates they encounter in their profession. Let people share their experiences, carefully consider questions that guide the conversation in the desired direction, and be flexible with the planned methods and activities in the workshop. Sometimes, you need to adapt them on the fly when the volcano of ideas erupts unexpectedly. In our workshop, we also adjusted the method by significantly reducing the planned volume of group work and working in groups only towards the end of the day to explore possibilities for using augmented reality in the classroom.

Example: questions for a co-ideation workshop set out by the Hunt Museum Living Lab

Setting: a co-ideation workshop at the Hunt Museum, with participants from Cultural Heritage institutions across Ireland and Limerick-based corporates who had CSR programmes interested in using them in a more meaningful way.

The plenary session involved participants sitting at tables in 3 groups, each with a mix of corporates and cultural heritage organisations. Using the canvas below, each group brainstormed answers to the question: **what are the areas where businesses and museums can add value to each other in delivering value for the community?**

Once this exercise was complete the participants were asked to contemplate the challenge of antisocial behaviour in public spaces, as this was the ‘challenge’ that the Hunt Museum wanted to address with their testing of the CSR CPBM.

RECHARGE Project Ideation Tool

<p>Problem </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the idea support museum's mission and strategy? • What is needed from the museum (human, intellectual, physical, and financial resources)? 				
	<p>Project Idea / Solution 2 </p>			

The groups were asked to discuss strategies, and in particular the need to understand the WHY - is this due to a lack of ownership of the space? A disengaged community in need of expression?

This exercise led to an ideation session focused specifically in the case of Hunt Museum, using the canvas below, paying special consideration to the question: What would the businesses and museums involved gain?

Iteration, Reflection and Selection

It is important to select a potential project idea(s) with your stakeholders that is achievable in the timeframe and resources given. As many potential ideas can emerge from the co-creation activities with stakeholders in your co-ideation workshop(s), here are some methods you can use to help reflect on, select and iterate the ideas generated.

- To help generate ideas, consider starting the process with conventional group work techniques, such as brainstorming, and then encouraging participants to select the most promising concepts, using a method such as dot-voting.
- Throughout the session you could guide the group in completing a comprehensive project canvas based on the identified best idea(s). This is a tool that helps in identifying current and potential stakeholders, foreseeing their future engagement with the project, and visualising the when and how of collaboration with project beneficiaries. This comprehensive approach transforms the concept into a tangible project draft.
- Another method to streamline project ideas is revisiting the Cultural Participatory Business Model (CPBM) Canvas during co-ideation workshops. Collaborate with stakeholders to populate the CPBM canvas for each (main) project idea. By mapping elements like the value proposition, involved parties, target audience, required activities, and associated costs and outcomes, you can more effectively evaluate the feasibility of each project idea.
- If working in smaller groups, prepare pitches for each main project idea to help everyone become more familiar with each idea.
- Make sure to collect feedback and eventual changes to proposed ideas. You can use tools such as [feedback cards](#) or [Open Space Technology](#).
- In groups, create an Action Plan for each viable project idea, outlining the smaller steps you would take to execute the project. This will help you to understand the feasibility of each idea. See the section below for guidance on creating an Action Plan.

The following questions might help you choose your project idea:

- What is achievable within the timeframe?
- What resources do we have available to us?
- What skill sets does each stakeholder bring?
- What relationships do we have that can bring added value to the participatory process?
- How much time can each stakeholder give to the project?

Once this decision has been made, you may need to revise the value proposition and complete or adjust your participatory business model canvas.

Example: Here is how the Prato Living Lab used the Cultural Participatory Business Model Canvas

Completing your CPBM canvas is an iterative process: in Prato Textile Museum we first filled it out before designing the whole Living Lab Process.

After our first co-ideation workshop we came back to our CPBM canvas and strongly revised it. Many insights were shared during the workshop by participants, and the outcomes of the workshop required several changes in the CPBM canvas. This was not the last time it would change! Indeed, during the implementation of the Living Lab process, many details became much clearer and allowed our team and partners to better understand operations, mutual relationships' channels and goals, feasibility of the proposed solutions and customers needs.

Create an Action Plan

Creating an effective action plan involves collaborative consideration and consistent follow-through for optimal outcomes. Here's a guide on how to craft an action plan in a few simple steps.

Define Your End Objectives

Begin by identifying your objective(s). Whether you're launching a new initiative or solving a problem, clarity is key to success. One way to create concrete objectives is to use the SMART criteria: Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Timely.

List Down the Steps to be Followed

Once your objective(s) is established, outline the necessary steps. Create a template detailing tasks, due dates, and responsible individuals. Ensure team-wide participation and access to the document. Clearly define and break down complex tasks into manageable components. You might want to consider using a RACI Matrix template as a guide to clarify project roles and responsibilities.

Prioritise Tasks and Add Deadlines

Organise your task list by prioritising and setting realistic deadlines. Identify tasks that may hinder progress if not prioritised and consult with task owners to determine feasible deadlines.

Set Milestones

Integrate milestones into your plan to create mini-goals leading to the final objective. Start from the end goal and work backward. Space milestones effectively, maintaining a balance between proximity and achievement. Milestones help you track your progress and create moments to celebrate!

Identify the Resources Needed

Ensure you have all required resources before initiating the project. Identify and plan to acquire necessary resources. Incorporate budget considerations into the action plan.

Visualise Your Action Plan

Create a visual representation for better understanding and can easily be shared. This can take the form of a flowchart, Gantt chart, or table. Ensure clarity in communicating tasks, owners, deadlines, and resources. Make the document easily accessible and editable for all team members.

By using some of these guideposts, you'll be well-equipped to create a comprehensive action plan that fosters clarity and collaboration!

Before you move to the next step, check if you have done the following:

- Chosen a project idea with stakeholders to develop your Cultural Participatory Business Model
- Created a clear value proposition with stakeholders
- Completed a Cultural Participatory Business Model Canvas
- Developed an action plan for your project idea

04. SET UP YOUR LIVING LAB PROJECT

Choosing a Project Management Methodology

IT'S TIME TO BRING YOUR CHOSEN PROJECT IDEA TO LIFE!

Before getting started with your project, it is helpful to set up some simple structures for working together. This is an opportunity to voice and align expectations. As the project develops you can also encourage the development of organic processes and ideas.

- Choose your **project management methodology**. Consider the **number of meetings**, the frequency of meetings, and the timeline and requirements needed to develop a product/service. You can choose from existing styles of working together, such as AGILE. .
- **Agree on which tools and platforms** you want to use to communicate and work together. This will help everyone to stay involved and ensure that important information isn't getting lost. The tools and platforms may need to change as the project progresses.
- Whichever style of collaboration you choose, remember to **maintain communication with all participants**, and if possible involve them in this decision. This will help to align expectations and choose a collaboration style that is achievable for everyone involved.

Example: Here is how the Hunt Museum Living Lab chose their project management methodology

Creating a collaboration setup for the Hunt Museum Living Lab involved integrating Agile methodologies, organising sprints, and implementing appropriate tools to facilitate effective teamwork and project management.

Agile is a project management methodology that emphasises iterative development, flexibility, and collaboration. Its key principles include regular adaptation to change, continuous improvement, and stakeholder involvement throughout the project.

Firstly we designated a Scrum Master responsible for facilitating the Agile process . This person was the project manager for the Hunt project, and had the overview of all the work being done by the various participants.

Once the goals and objectives are defined they were broken up into manageable tasks and organised using the project management tool Trello. Tasks were split up into sprints, which were typically 4 weeks long, with weekly team meetings. At the end of each sprint, a review meeting was held with participants to demonstrate the completed work and gather feedback. Additionally, we discussed what went well, what could be improved, and action items for the next sprint – make sure that this is an open conversation where all participants are receptive to critique and not afraid to give it!

Be open to changing requirements and continuously refine the actions to be taken based on feedback and evolving needs. This helps in aligning the project with everyone's expectations and needs!

Set up Key Performance Indicators for the Living Lab Project

Assessing the impact of your project is an important part of the Living Lab methodology. Creating and measuring Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will help you to demonstrate the impact of your project and whether you managed to achieve your value proposition. KPIs are quantifiable measurements that capture desired results and outputs. Defining these together with stakeholders can be helpful for agreeing on priorities. **This should be a group exercise.**

In order to get a complete picture, it is important to define these KPIs at the start of your project and assess them over time. You need time to understand the change you are generating through your actions.

How to do this:

Break down your value proposition into specific objectives that can be measured -. f.eg. number and gender of stakeholders involved in your actions, number of events, use of institutional resources, etc.. Need inspiration? Have a look at the **Europeana standardised question bank**.

In the design phase, try to think especially across social, economic, organisational, and environmental areas of impact. Do you think a relevant impact area is missing? Feel free to add it to your assessment. It is crucial that impacts you want to assess and understand are tailored to your project's scope. Universal KPIs fitting everyone do not exist.

The 4 recommended areas of impact to be taken into account are:

- **Social** - analyses changes the Living Labs have on the involved communities, their motivation, well-being, social cohesion and sense of belonging, etc. How many and who are your volunteers? Why are they involved? How does the involvement change their everyday lives?
- **Economic** - examines the effect of the Living Lab process and activities on the economic side of things for the involved stakeholders. It usually measures changes in business revenue, business profits, personal wages, and/or jobs.
- **Organisational** - looks at possible internal changes in organisations involved in works of the Living Labs - was there a change in organisational strategy? Were new workflows or jobs created to address the needs of the Living Labs process?
- **Environmental** - accounts for the environmental values of actions performed under the Living Labs and understands their impact on the environment, like the production of carbon dioxide.

Once you have agreed upon the KPIs for your project with your stakeholders, create a schedule for when you will collect data and choose the methods you will use for that (eg. surveys, interviews, analytics, etc.). You want to have some time between these assessments to allow change to happen but you also need to make the plan realistic and operate within the project's timeline. Planning is key.

Example: These are the KPIs co-designed by the Hunt Museum Living Lab with their stakeholders to measure their impact:

Area of Impact	KPI	Measurement Criteria
Social	Local Communities regain heritage skills and a sense of belonging to the museum.	<p>Number of workshops</p> <p>Numbers of community attendees of willow weaving workshops</p> <p>Numbers who feel they have gained a new heritage skill</p>
Environmental	Museum actively seen as contributing to local climate targets.	<p><i>Based on Limerick city biodiversity plan:</i></p> <p>Facilitated construction of woven willow roosting platforms, bat and a variety of bird nest boxes and insect ‘hotels’ throughout the City</p> <p>Enhance the biodiversity of Limerick City for future generations and to educate and promote the importance of Limerick City’s biodiversity for all.</p> <p>Raise awareness, general interest and knowledge of biodiversity through a variety of media.</p>

Example: These are the KPIs co-designed by the Hunt Museum Living Lab with their stakeholders to measure their impact:

Area of Impact	KPI	Measurement Criteria
Organisational	The reputation of the Hunt Museum as an innovative and inclusive organisation is enhanced.	<p>Number of workshops</p> <p>Numbers of community attendees of willow weaving workshops</p> <p>Numbers who feel they have gained a new heritage skill</p>
Economic	CSR hours contribute directly to a museum project while improving the wellbeing of their workforce, the local community and the environment.	<p><i>Living Willow sculptures are in position</i></p> <p><i>Company willow weaving workshops contribute to staff happiness reducing absenteeism, improving staff retention</i></p> <p><i>Cook Living Willow CSR partnership is maintained over 3 years</i></p>

Before you move to the next step, check if you have done the following:

- Agreement on how often you will be meeting, platforms and tools
- Measurable Key Performance Indicators and when and how to collect data

05. RUNNING A LIVING LAB PROJECT

Execution of the Action Plan

Embarking on the execution of your project's action plan involves a systematic approach. Begin by thoroughly reviewing the plan, ensuring a clear grasp of goals, timelines, and allocated resources. Collaboratively review and assign responsibilities clearly to team members, fostering accountability and a shared understanding of individual contributions. Establish clear communication channels, monitor progress diligently, and be ready to adapt to unforeseen challenges.

Also celebrate achievements as you reach milestones, fostering a positive work environment. While it might seem time consuming, do document your lessons learned as these will guide your decisions in future projects. Successful execution is not just about completing tasks; it's about achieving desired outcomes and laying the groundwork for future successes.

Regular check-ins and reporting

Consistent check-ins and regular reporting are essential components of effective project management and team collaboration. Here are guideposts on how to hold meetings to iterate an action plan and structure reporting:

Checking in

Schedule in the meetings that you agreed upon with your stakeholders. Try to create a consistent schedule as regularity will help in maintaining momentum.

For each meeting clearly outline the objectives of the meeting. Setting specific goals and an agenda for meetings will keep the discussion focused. Develop a structured agenda together with team members/stakeholders to guide the meeting. Include key discussion points such as progress updates, challenges faced, action items, and opportunities for improvement. Are you reviewing progress, identifying challenges, or refining the action plan? Certain project management methodologies, such as AGILE, also include recommendations for what to discuss.

Within your meetings foster a culture of feedback, capture decisions that were made, and action items assigned, and set actionable next steps. However, this also includes celebrating milestones and iterating when you identify roadblocks and challenges with your action plan.

Be mindful of the budget

Being mindful of a budget in a project is crucial for its success and sustainability. Begin by thoroughly understanding the budget. Know the allocated funds, cost categories, and any financial constraints. Then if possible locate a contingency budget to account for unforeseen circumstances. This provides a safety net for unexpected expenses and helps prevent budget overruns.

Implement a robust system for monitoring expenses regularly. Track both committed and actual expenditures. Establish clear approval processes for any budget changes. Require proper documentation and justification before approving adjustments to the budget. This helps maintain control over spending.

Foster transparent communication about the budget with all stakeholders. Keep the project team informed of budget status, challenges, and any adjustments made. Transparency builds trust and allows for collaborative problem-solving.

Make Sure Everything is Participatory

Actively involve your community! Use proactive communication to let them know how the project is going, what you have tried and learned, and your next steps. Maintaining consistent communication is not just about transparency and accountability but also building trust and ownership with everyone involved.

Integrate participation to create a shared understanding and shared sense of ownership of a project. The decisions made with your participants as a result of discussions and mutual agreements should base the of the trajectory of your project.

Identify and stick to your data collection moments (KPIs): Regular Reporting

Mindset

Maintaining a practical mindset and leveraging strong project management skills is essential for running the reporting process efficiently. Be open and responsive to the project's scope, considering both opportunities and limitations. Embrace the unpredictability of the process and view surprises as opportunities for improvement.

Reporting results and outputs

Reporting results and outputs is a critical aspect of project management, as it provides stakeholders with insights into the project's progress and performance. Before creating a report, identify your target audience. Tailor the level of detail and focus of your report to meet the needs of your audience. Tip: Establish a consistent format for your reports. Be specific and use quantifiable metrics whenever possible.

Before you move to the next step, check if you have done the following:

- Assigned responsibilities based on your action plan
- Scheduled regular meetings and outlined meeting objectives
- Made a thorough budget and shared it with stakeholders
- Created a template for your reporting

06. EVALUATION OF LL RESULTS AGAINST KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

Well done on finishing your project! The last step is to evaluate the impact and results with your stakeholders and project team.

Critical Reflection

Is the project complete? Have you reached your goals? What was missing? What can you improve next time? These are some of the questions you might ask after finishing the project. Evaluating a project is a vital step in the project management lifecycle, providing valuable insights for improvement and future success. Critical reflection on the process is key to understanding the completeness of the project and identifying areas for enhancement.

- Reflect on the project to identify missing elements, considering documentation, stakeholder engagement, resource allocation, and other vital components.
- Identify areas for improvement and schedule a post-project review meeting with key stakeholders to foster open discussions about strengths and weaknesses.
- Gather feedback from the project team, focusing on challenges, successes, and improvement suggestions.
- Additionally, engage with project stakeholders to obtain valuable external perspectives for a comprehensive evaluation.

Strategies for critical reflection:

- SWOT Analysis
- Lessons Learned Session
- Benchmarking

Outcomes and Outputs

During the last phase of your project it is important to assess the tangible deliverables or outputs generated by the project. This could include completed tasks, produced goods, or delivered services.

- Understand how far you've come and where you are by measuring these outputs against predetermined criteria to determine their quality and completeness. You might have included these criteria in your KPIs.
- Compare actual results against the planned outcomes and outputs. Identify any variances and analyse the reasons behind them.
- Additionally, outside of the tangible outputs, there may be broader outcomes of the project. These are the changes or impacts resulting from the project outputs in a longer term. When evaluating the outcomes assess whether the outcomes align with the initial objectives and if they contribute positively to the overall project goals. Assess unintended consequences, both positive and negative, that may have resulted from the project. This helps in understanding the broader impact beyond the initially defined outcomes.

Analyse and interpret the data around your KPIs

Understanding your impact and crafting a compelling narrative around it is crucial for effective communication, discussion, and learning from your experiences. Throughout your Living Lab project you will have collected quantitative and qualitative data for your KPIs to help understand your impact. Once you have analysed and interpreted this data, you can use it to communicate your impact to others.

- Look at quantitative data related to goals achieved, observed changes, or other relevant indicators, and see what insights you can gain
- Then you can complement your quantitative data with qualitative insights. Collect stories, testimonials, and anecdotes that showcase the human side of your impact. This will add depth and authenticity to your narrative.
- Finally, craft a narrative that brings together your objectives, outcomes, and stakeholder perspectives. Use a storytelling approach to emotionally engage your audience. Share the challenges you faced, the milestones achieved, and the valuable lessons learned. Highlight how your impact contributes to sustainability. Emphasise long-term effects and ongoing benefits, making it clear that your efforts extend well beyond immediate outcomes.

LIVING LABS SAMPLE TOOLBOX

Participatory Approaches and Exercises to Implement Your Living Lab Project

In the context of Recharge, "**participatory approaches**" refer to a set of methods, strategies, and principles that actively involve and engage relevant stakeholders in the planning, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation processes of the project. These approaches emphasise the importance of inclusivity, collaboration, and empowerment, aiming to ensure that all stakeholders have a voice, contribute their knowledge and perspectives, and have a sense of ownership and responsibility over the project.

Embarking on a journey of inclusive and collaborative initiatives, participatory exercises stand as the bedrock of meaningful engagement within the Recharge project. This sample set of exercises encapsulates some of the methodologies, strategies, and principles that actively involve stakeholders in shaping the trajectory of the project. The activities outlined in this section fall under the following categories:

Exploratory exploratory activities are focused on understanding the problem or challenge the project will address. This might involve brainstorming, research, analysis, and exploration to gain insights into the context, needs of various participants, and any constraints.

Generative generative activities use the insights gained through exploration and observation to generate a wide range of creative ideas and potential solutions. It is about ideating and conceptualising different solutions and project possibilities.

Evaluative evaluative activities might be oriented around testing and refining products, activities, or concepts. It aims to gather feedback, assess the effectiveness of the design, and make informed decisions for improvements.

WORLD CAFE

Time	Group Size	Activity Type	Materials
60-120 min	10+	Generative	Flip chart, markers, post-its

OVERVIEW

The World Cafe is a workshop activity with a *two-decade history*, designed to foster engaging thematic conversations among participants to explore the general sentiments of participants concerning certain ideas and themes or get feedback. This method, coined by Juanita Brown, is both straightforward and influential, allowing for meaningful discussions guided entirely by the participants and the subjects that hold significance for them. Facilitators establish a cafe-like environment and offer uncomplicated guidelines. Subsequently, participants autonomously organise themselves to delve into a curated set of pertinent topics or questions for discussion.

IMPLEMENTATION

- Setup small café-style tables in rooms and seat 4 or 5 Participants at each. These are your ‘conversation clusters’.
- The Facilitator then explains to the group they will now have 3 rounds of conversation of approximately 20-30 minutes each.
- Questions or issues that genuinely matter to your work, life or community are discussed while other groups explore similar questions at nearby tables.
- The Facilitator encourages the table members to write, doodle, and draw key ideas on their paper tablecloths or to note key ideas on large index cards or placemats in the centre of the group.

- After completing the 1st round of conversation, the Facilitator asks each table to agree on a 'table host' who remains at the table while the others travel to different tables. *You can also assign table hosts from the beginning, they can be co facilitators in your organisation. This is not a hard rule for running the activity.*
- The travellers now get up from the table and move to another. They can go to whichever table they prefer carrying with them key ideas, themes and questions from their old table into their new conversations.
- The Facilitator asks the Table Hosts to welcome their new guests and briefly share the main ideas, themes and questions from the initial conversation (max 2 mins). Encourage guests to link and connect ideas coming from their previous table conversations – listening carefully and building on each other's contributions.
- At the end of the 2nd round, all of the tables and conversations will be cross-pollinated with insights from previous conversations.
- In the 3rd round of conversation, people can return to their home (original) tables to synthesise their discoveries, or they may continue on to new tables, leaving the same or a new host at the table.
- An optional step is for the Facilitator to pose a new question that helps deepen the exploration for the 3rd round of conversation.
- After your 3rd round of conversation, initiate a period of sharing discoveries and insights in a whole group conversation.
- Make sure you have someone flip-chart this plenary conversation so you capture any patterns, knowledge and actions that emerge.

TO CONSIDER IN YOUR ACTIVITY DESIGN

Define your objectives

Is your objective to develop a number of ideas? Engage more diversity of perspective? Get nuanced feedback through conversations among participants?

This activity is a great opportunity for people to converse but defining your objectives can help approach how you get the best results possible. For example you can:

- In the instructions, include a request for three big ideas from each group at each table.
- Ask participants to frame their response within the scope of their work or expertise to frame responses through specific perspectives

Roles

- Hosts can support a group diligently following a specific line of conversation which might be easier if they stay at a single table throughout the session
- For sharing sessions ask participants at the beginning of the session that they will share their results and might want to assign roles such as:
 - Note taker
 - Presenter
 - Time keeper

FISH BOWL

Time	Group Size	Activity Type	Materials
60-120 minutes	6+	Exploratory	Video meeting platform

OVERVIEW

Conducting an online FishBowl activity represents an effective approach to ensure the active involvement of all participants in the conversation. The core of the Fishbowl lies in its unique structure: a specific group of participants is encouraged to keep their cameras and microphones active, creating the distinctive "fishbowl" on the screen, while others temporarily deactivate their cameras and microphones. In this dynamic setting, those inside the fishbowl engage in a conversation, posing questions and sharing insights on a selected topic. Concurrently, participants with deactivated cameras and microphones take on the role of attentive listeners, fostering a well-balanced exchange between active contributors and engaged audience members throughout the Fishbowl discussion.

In a Fishbowl discussion participants take turns being in the 'fishbowl'. Participants in the fishbowl discuss a topic while those outside the fishbowl listen attentively to their conversation. Turns are taken until everyone has been inside the 'fishbowl' so that everyone takes turns being contributors and listeners.

Fishbowl discussions can be great for facilitating sessions where people are working across disciplines to see each group's perspectives such as researchers, artists, policy makers etc.

IMPLEMENTATION

1. At the start of your activity explain in plain terms how the activity is going to go and remind participants that if they have a doubt or a question to be open and curious. It is okay to ask simple questions. Working with a diverse range of participants can be slow whether it is across disciplines, geographies etc. Much of the work in engaging and creating networks is through work through and across translating what we know and who we are.
2. Remind everyone to be mindful of being good listeners, not all questions might have immediate answers. This activity is less about solutions and more about learning to work together.
3. The discussion groups and fishbowl rounds should be predetermined to make the activity go along smoothly. The time for each group should be determined by group size. For example, if there are 4 people in a group, 20 minutes might be enough for a fishbowl discussion with the idea that each person has 5 minutes of speaking time.
4. Allot enough time at the end to conduct a quick moment to conclude the session where participants can share what they learned, were surprised by, or what they are still curious about.

TO CONSIDER IN YOUR ACTIVITY DESIGN

Make sure as facilitator that you take time to help folks understand the technology instructions whether you are using zoom, Google Meet or any other platform.

STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

Time	Group Size	Activity Type	Materials
40-60 minutes	3+	Generative	Post-its, canvas, markers

OVERVIEW

Stakeholder maps are a visual method to identify and consolidate who are the main constituents of a project and set the stage to centre those who are most likely to benefit and be impacted by your project. The primary advantage of utilising a stakeholder map lies in gaining visibility into individuals who hold sway over your initiatives and understanding the relationships among them. By charting out pertinent stakeholders, you enhance your ability to engage with them effectively and prioritise relationship development with key collaborators within your organisational framework.

Stakeholder maps are often speculative in nature with your team brainstorming people who may have an interest in your project. Therefore try to be as comprehensive as you can and include everyone who might benefit, who might be adversely affected, to those who might hold key resources or be critical to connecting with different groups and communities.

Stakeholders can be general types of people such as students, doctors, drivers etc. or specific people. The initial process can be done as a sketch or with post its. The version of this activity conducted in the Prato Living Lab made use of a bullseye canvas.

IMPLEMENTATION

1. Explain the main idea of the activity and an overview of the session. Pass out post-its to participants or explain how the online canvas will work depending on whether the session is online or offline.
2. Ask participants to try and be as exhaustive as they can in mapping out stakeholders especially in terms of being open to working with lesser represented groups or communities.
3. Give the group 7-12 minutes per section of the bullseye canvas
4. At the end you might ask participants what they observe i.e. what are some clear trends on the board by grouping similar responses, what are some surprises on the board, and what communication strategies might be needed whether by groups of stakeholders or by proximity they have to the project.

TEMPLATES

Various formats exist for stakeholder mapping, but this approach is one of the most straightforward for initiating the process. The Bullseye model provides a concise summary of all individuals connected to the product, regardless of their significance.

Whether you possess ample information or not, this method serves as a useful starting point for shaping the conversation. Adjustments can always be made later as you uncover more insights through your research.

Core: At the centre of the canvas you have your core stakeholders. This circle is small because we want to sharpen our focus. Write down the main stakeholder(s) that is impacted by the project you want to conduct or problem you want to solve

.

Internal: Just outside the core are your internal stakeholders. They are those who will consistently provide input and move the project forward.

External: Outside the internal stakeholders are the external stakeholders. They will likely be those who will stay updated to date with the project, provide feedback when consulted, and support dissemination activities.

BULLSEYE TEMPLATE

FEEDBACK CARDS

Time	Group Size	Activity Type	Materials
60-120 min	4+	Evaluative	Post-its or cards

OVERVIEW

Feedback cards is a method adapted by the Prato Museum inspired by Open Space Technology. This method is a flexible means to elicit and collect feedback from a group discussion. While Open Space Technology uses the method to talk about broad, complex themes, the team at Prato adapted the method to use it to discuss pitches as well as to structure feedback discussions to validate and test products and services.

IMPLEMENTATION

1. To start the activity participants should be welcomed and invited to sit within a circle. Once everyone is seated and settled the facilitator should then provide an introduction to what the group will discuss in a clear and concrete manner. This means giving an overview of the activity, how the group sessions will be structured, and the expected output.
2. Then participants will be asked to put together the agenda i.e. the ideas or pitches around the theme or topic of the group discussion. Participants should be encouraged to with a piece of paper or post-its write down a pitch, issue, or question in regards to the theme or topic. In writing their post-it they should write their name on the post-it, and will be responsible for hosting a group discussion, documenting important points made in the discussion.
3. Once everyone has finished writing each person who would like to contribute to the agenda with their post it will read their post-it and then place it on a common board.
4. Facilitators should keep in mind how many ideas or pitches are on the board and divide the remaining time so that participants can spend time in a group discussion for each idea. Those who have proposed an idea or pitch should be supplied with sharpies, paper, etc to help document and host a group discussion. Participants should then decide which post-it idea or pitch they would like to go to first. Then facilitators will keep time and ask participants to switch groups until participants have gone to each group discussion area proposed (however this is dependent on the amount of time for the activity).
5. At the end of the group discussions hosts of each group discussion will hang their documentation on a wall for participants to read and observe.
6. Concluding the session is most effectively done by providing participants with the chance to express their thoughts on how they experienced the activity and the key takeaways. In the case of large groups where giving everyone individual time is impractical, hearing from a few participants still offers a comprehensive overview due to the shared nature of the experience.
7. When you sense that all relevant points or issues have been shared, close the session with the next steps and noting what you appreciated and learned from the day.

WHAT IS THE RECHARGE PLATFORM?

Decidim

The main piece of software used in Recharge is the participatory platform. It is open source and based on Decidim. Decidim, from the Catalan 'We decide', is a platform, a digital infrastructure for participatory democracy, free and open source, for cities and organisations. Decidim is open source. An open-source code can be used, modified, improved and redistributed under the same licence by anyone, which is why it was chosen for Recharge. Created by the city of Barcelona, Decidim is an online space where participants can deliberate and make decisions in a transparent way in collaboration with their stakeholders and communities.

101 Building Your Own Participatory Space

But Decidim is much more than that: 'participatory democracy' refers to that form of 'government of the people, for the people and by the people' in which people participate as equals. On Decidim, platform users (participants) interact through participatory mechanisms or features on the platform known as components within different participatory spaces that channel their democratic power towards specific outcomes such as creating communities, collaborations, and transparent decision making.

THE RECHARGE PLATFORM AND THE LIVING LABS

The Recharge Platform serves as a platform for the Living Labs to conduct activities, record, and share their progress. It serves as both the online presence of the project and a digital place and tool at the disposal of the living labs. The platform aims to serve as an open source tool and space for labs to experiment, explore, and develop a more participatory approach to the digital facet of their work.

The screenshot displays three Living Lab cards on the Recharge Platform. Each card features a header image, a title, a brief description, and a 'MORE INFO' button.

- Hunt Living Lab:** The Hunt Living Lab aims to bring together active communities, with companies looking to obtain mean...
- Prato Living Lab:** New participatory business models are needed for museums to reach economic sustainability and serve ...
- EMM Living Lab:** The Estonian Maritime Museum's Living Lab will test the idea, that the cultural heritage sector is r...

AN ONLINE PLATFORM BUILT FOR TRANSPARENT AND ACCOUNTABLE PARTICIPATION

Participatory Spaces: Processes and Assemblies

Decidim's design is oriented around the notion of creating more participatory spaces online. So to conduct activities with the various features or components such as surveys or meetings you first need to create the type of participatory space.

The types of spaces are as follows: processes, assemblies, conferences, initiatives, consultations, and voting. However for the purpose of the Recharge platform the more used spaces are processes, assemblies, and conferences that have been repurposed and customised for Recharge. All the spaces serve a similar function of creating a space where activities can be hosted but have unique qualities that set them apart. For example processes can be grouped i.e. there can be process groups and a process is demarcated by phases. While assemblies are understood to be a series of interactions not necessarily defined by phases there can be sub-assemblies that fall under the umbrella of another assembly.

HOW TO CREATE A PROCESS IN 5 MINUTES?

THE BASICS: COMPONENTS

Within assemblies, processes, and conferences administrators can add specific activities. These activities on Decidim are referred to as components.

iFrame Component: Then there is the iFrame component, which you would use to integrate a page or an external link into our process. Iframes can be used for MIRO boards and Google Docs you want to connect to your process. Your ability to see what is displayed in the iFrame depends on your log-in to that specific platform. For example, if it were a google doc with limited access rights then you may not be able to see what the iFrame is meant to display depending on the settings of the external website, platform or page.

Blog: The blog component works like a real blog where you can post news or new articles which users can comment on and follow. The blog component is currently being used for the Recharge Diary.

Budget: The budget component is used to make participatory budgets. For projects or communities that want to collaboratively work transparently on a budget, this might be a useful option in the future.

Debates: The debates component which as its very name indicates contains various discussions and functions like a discussion thread. Participants can be enabled to create their own discussion threads based on topics they find relevant.

Meetings: Meetings as is evidenced by the name are created to host the details of a meeting. Meetings can show the meeting time, agenda, the link to the streaming, an etherpad for collective notes, and even enable the registration function. In short, multiple functions can serve for any type of meeting, be it physical, virtual or hybrid. Meetings have been used often and frequently within each of the Living Labs for their events.

Page: The page component creates a blank page where you can insert static content such as an FAQ or 'About' page. They are static and can include images or videos.

Proposals: The proposals component allows for administrators and participants to create proposals that can then be evaluated, commented on or rejected. Whether or not they are accepted or rejected is demonstrated by their status. Additionally, you can show whether or not proposals have come from a meeting.

Sortition: The sortition component randomly selects various proposals. The sortition components allow for a non-biased selection. For example, if selecting people to participate on a committee one could create a proposal for each possible participant and use sortition to decide the final participants.

Survey: The survey component allows us to ask questions in both closed and open formats such as multiple choice questions or open ended text questions.

ANNEX

The Recharge Glossary

Living Labs

Living Labs are dynamic spaces where ideas and solutions can be co-created, tested, and iterated by collaborating stakeholders. The Living Lab offers methods for cultural heritage institutions, researchers, industry, communities, and government to co-design concrete solutions in real-life environments. Operating as 'innovation zones', Living Labs can bring together community knowledge with professional expertise for action-based projects.

Stakeholders

is anyone potentially influenced directly or indirectly, positively or negatively, by the CHIs practices and participatory activities. Stakeholders are defined independently of who actually participates in (or is invited to) a decision-making process, for instance the society at large may experience consequences of solutions implemented within participatory activities. Stakeholders can be categorised as: government sector, private sector (for profit), civic sector (non-profit), and citizens. Stakeholders can also be categorised based on the form of their participation: information, consultation, involvement, collaboration or empowerment.

Stakeholders can be recognized in one or more of the following categories:

- **Participant** - is any actor taking part in the decision-making process based on a position granted by the decision making process organiser. This can apply to certain interest groups or the general public, be restricted to specifically invited individuals, certain experts, state agencies, organisations and formal and informal groups or apply to no one at all.

- **Beneficiaries** - are people who the Living Labs hope to serve, the intended recipients of the project's benefits and are expected to experience positive changes or improvements in their lives, circumstances, or environments as a result of the project's interventions. They are, firstly, the direct users who consume and use some of the goods and services derived, generally for a price. We also consider passive users, who are interested in the existence, legacy, and option value of a museum even if they do not consume it, and who express their willingness to pay through taxes or donations. Finally, we also consider as beneficiaries those groups that benefit from the computable and uncomputable externalities of a museum, in terms of knowledge increase, social value of heritage, or urban reputation value.
- **Public** - is anybody who is exposed to the information about the project and/or its results without taking any active part in it, eg. through online and offline communication.
- **Customers** - are all direct users of any of the goods and services provided by a museum / Living Lab in a broad sense, usually for a fee. Therefore, we are dealing firstly with visitors to museums, who enjoy their cultural programme for personal, leisure, educational or research purposes. We also consider those who participate in other income-generating activities such as shopping in the museum boutique, or attending special events or educational programmes. We add users of new digital and multimedia supplies. We could also consider club users, such as the members of the museum, members of supporting societies, who have discounts or access advantages to exclusive events.
- **Funding stakeholders** - are people who will finance your Living Lab model with any level of engagement, as participants, as beneficiaries, or as public.

Engagement

Engagement is a set of heterogeneous and articulated processes, actions and organisational behaviours aimed at developing relations and mutuality in between two or more parties. Specifically, the purpose of community engagement is to develop and sustain a “working relationship between one or more organisations and one or more community groups, to help them both understand and act on the needs or issues that the community experience.” (Scottish National Occupational Standards for Community Engagement)

Community

The term "community" refers to a group of people at the grassroots. This is a group of people who are closely connected and involved in activities or issues at the local level who have a direct interest in and impact on the well-being, development, and affairs of their immediate geographical or social area. This community can encompass for example; local residents, local education bodies, health and wellbeing groups, family groups, children's clubs, artists, professional groups and more. The concept of community in this context emphasises inclusivity and the engagement of multiple perspectives and voices.

Cultural Heritage Institutions

In the contexts of the RECHARGE project, **CHIs** are concerned with the protection, conservation, interpretation, research, and access of tangible and intangible cultural and scientific heritage.

Need-based cooperation

Need-based cooperation refers to the collaborative approach to value capture for generating inclusive and equitable benefits to all parties involved, by understanding the needs and motivations of actors in the value network. This is a key element in RECHARGE participatory business models.

Participatory approaches

In the context of the RECHARGE project, "participatory approaches" refer to a set of methods, strategies, and principles that actively involve and engage relevant stakeholders in the planning, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation processes of the project. These approaches emphasise the importance of inclusivity, collaboration, and empowerment, aiming to ensure that all stakeholders have a voice, contribute their knowledge and perspectives, and have a sense of ownership and responsibility over the project.

Capacity-building

“process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that organisations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world. An essential ingredient in capacity-building is transformation that is generated and sustained over time from within; transformation of this kind goes beyond performing tasks to changing mindsets and attitudes.” (source:

<https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>)

Participatory business model

Participatory business models are experimental approaches to value-creation, value-capturing, and value-delivery that include a broad spectrum of stakeholders. They reflect the process that make businesses, organisations, and institutions' operations desirable, feasible, and financially viable by leveraging their networks. Through engaged contribution, participatory business models devise sustainable solutions and organisations involved gain resilience.

By applying participatory approaches to business model-making and development, PBMs present three main characteristics:

1. Co-innovate to remain relevant and unique;
2. Develop solutions with various degrees of co-ownership;
3. Make innovations emerge from inclusive needs-based cooperation.

Financial viability

Within RECHARGE, financial viability refers to the long-term survival of a participatory effort in the changing environment, which sometimes requires redesigning structures and replanning activities. Financial viability refers to the financial livability of a participatory effort. Some would argue that the relationship between viability and sustainability is circular: if an entity succeeds in living, it can develop sustainable strategies, but not inversely. If an entity is being perceived as sustainable, it will attract the means to keep its head above water.

Value

Value has to do with the comparison of goods based on the classification and categorisation of characteristics that lead to a preference or choice. Goods can be compared based on price (currency value scale), uniqueness (cultural value scale), or looks (aesthetic value scale). As such, value is socially constructed, it is generated dynamically, it can be various, and variable, it depends on social conventions, and is influenced by information available to make the comparison.

Value capture

Value capturing refers to the ability to benefit from a process' results, which can be understood in the form of revenues (monetary), reach (the amount of people who can benefit from the offered products and services), and reputation (the improvement of the organisation's image). This is the value generated for the Cultural Heritage Institution.

Value proposition

Value capturing refers to the ability to benefit from a process' results, which can be understood in the form of revenues (monetary), reach (the amount of people who can benefit from the offered products and services), and reputation (the improvement of the organisation's image). This is the value generated for the Cultural Heritage Institution.

Value creation

Value creation refers to the development of products or services that an organisation offers on the basis of its customers' needs, and therefore its reason for being. Value is created when resources are transformed, to make a painting, to communicate a story, or to reposition an idea. This is the value generated of the product or service.

Value capture

Value capturing refers to the ability to benefit from a process' results, which can be understood in the form of revenues (monetary), reach (the amount of people who can benefit from the offered products and services), and reputation (the improvement of the organisation's image). This is the value generated for the Cultural Heritage Institution.

Co-ownership

As part of the participatory practices of business model architecture, Co-ownership refers to sharing ownership, which implies involvement in the decision-making process, the funding of the initiative, as well as sharing the benefits derived among partners. It requires trust and transparency of operations that are fundamental conditions to fuel the sustainability of cooperation, prioritising the common project over the interests of individual actors.

Co-governance

As part of the participatory practices of business model architecture, Co-governance refers to an approach to management and decision-making in which multiple stakeholders actively and collaboratively participate in the strategic direction of a cultural institution. Rather than having a hierarchical and centralised leadership structure, co-governance involves the inclusion of diverse perspectives and voices in the decision-making process. Co-governance also promotes transparency and accountability, as decision-making is shared and subject to scrutiny from multiple actors. Nonetheless, it can also be resource-intensive and would require trust-building and clear decision structures.

Co-ideation and Co-creation

Co-ideation often serves as an initial stage or a part of the process within co-creation. In co-creation, ideas generated through co-ideation are further refined, developed, and implemented with the active involvement and collaboration of stakeholders. Co-ideation helps to generate a diverse pool of ideas, while co-creation involves turning these ideas into tangible outcomes by integrating the inputs of various stakeholders.

Co-ideation focuses on the generation and refinement of ideas through collaboration, while co-creation extends this collaboration to the entire process of creating, delivering, and evolving a product, service, or solution by involving diverse stakeholders. Both processes emphasise teamwork, inclusivity, and leveraging collective intelligence to achieve innovative and meaningful results.

Collaboration

Collaboration refers to the cooperative and participatory process of working together among various stakeholders, including citizens, organisations, and government bodies, to collectively contribute, share ideas, and harness the power of collective intelligence, perspectives and expertise to address complex challenges and find innovative solutions. Collaboration within RECHARGE emphasises inclusivity, transparency, and active involvement of all participants. It fosters a culture of cooperation and joint effort, where individuals with diverse backgrounds, perspectives, and expertise come together to exchange knowledge, co-create proposals, deliberate, and reach consensus on important issues.

Participation

Participation refers to taking an active part in a project, an activity, or a process in which the participants's contribution influences the shape and/or results of the entire endeavour. Participation can take a form of various levels of involvement – from small short-term contributions, through larger involvement over a longer period of time, to long-standing relationships between the institution and a given group or an individual. It can also provide various forms of involvement: co-ownership, co-governance, co-creation, collaboration.

Financial sustainability

The concept refers to the financial capacity to maintain or expand the activities linked to CHIs mission, taking into account the resources available and the expenses derived from the activity, seeking a proper balance between both, generating revenue and controlling expenses, while also keeping the quality of cultural supply. In the short term, financial sustainability implies the capacity to face unforeseen difficulties such as the loss of funds for a programme or fluctuations in private donations. From a long-term perspective, financial sustainability refers to the entity's capacity to face the activities derived from its mission, for which it will be necessary to plan an active fundraising and strategic allocation.

Sustainability

Defined by the UN as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” It implies careful use of renewable (and especially) non-renewable resources. Sustainability is often broken down into 3 interconnected domains of social sustainability, environmental sustainability and economic sustainability. To achieve sustainable development, the domains have to be balanced. See also: ICOM, Sustainable Development Goals, New European Bauhaus.

Growth

In the context of RECHARGE, the growth desired for the CHI sector should be inclusive and green. Alternative approaches include post-growth and degrowth, which criticise and move beyond the concept of growth, “... aim[ing] to steer policy-making towards multiple economic, social and environmental goals rather than treating growth as an end in itself.” Many if not all of these approaches emphasise that society needs to operate within the boundaries of the planet and uphold social wellbeing and economic justice for everyone.

Impact

Changes that occur for relevant Stakeholders or in Society as a result of certain actions or activities (*definition after Europeana Impact Framework*)

Resilience

Resilience is the ability of a system, community or society to not only withstand challenges but also recover from the effects and undergo transitions to continue to develop in a sustainable manner.

(Open) Innovation

Open innovation embodies a collaborative and open knowledge method that generates, refines, and applies inventive ideas, solutions, and processes. Its essence lies in shared value creation through collaborative efforts and the exchange of resources among diverse stakeholders. By transcending conventional limits and emphasising shared ownership and mutual advantages, open innovation drives the evolution of participatory business models, capacity-building, financial sustainability, and the overall growth and durability of cultural heritage institutions and associated domains.